

1 **Title**

2 **Bridging the Sustainable Development Goals: A Multi-Label Text Classification**
3 **Approach for Mapping and Visualizing Nexuses in Sustainability Research**

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29 **Highlights**

30 Natural language processing models that can classify texts into Global Goals and
31 Targets of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were developed.

32

33 Transformer-based models RoBERTa, DeBERTa, and LUKE were employed and
34 trained by multi-labeled corpus obtained from diverse sectors.

35

36 Multi-label text classification models achieved high generalization performance in the
37 classification task using the OSDG Community Dataset.

38

39 A total of 160 thousand scientific articles including “sustainable development” were
40 collected from Scopus, and the scientific attention and nexuses among the SDGs
41 were visualized.

42

43 The uneven distribution of scientific attention to the SDGs was inferred, and notable
44 innovation hubs were detected.

45

46 Performance improvements were provided, the potential of large language models
47 was examined, and the SDG nexus was bridged.

48

49 **Abstract**

50 This study examines the performance of multi-label text classification models (i.e.,
51 Robustly optimized Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
52 (BERT) approach (RoBERTa), Decoding-enhanced BERT with disentangled attention
53 (DeBERTa), and Language Understanding with Knowledge-based Embeddings
54 (LUKE)) in an effort to automatically semantically map Global Goals and Targets of
55 the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Trained on a diverse, multisectoral
56 corpus, the models demonstrate high generalizability, especially the LUKE model,
57 which achieved strong recall on the OSDG Community Dataset. Applying this model
58 to a large corpus of scientific articles on sustainable development, we revealed an
59 uneven distribution of scientific attention that favors environmental sustainability over
60 social issues, such as equality and justice. Network analysis identified key nexuses in
61 areas of environmental, social, and economic sustainability. The model's utility in
62 identifying bridging research areas indicates that sustainable consumption and
63 production for all gender and biomass energy for circular bioeconomy can provide
64 integrated approaches to achieving the SDGs. Future research integrating generative
65 language models is suggested to enhance SDG classifier development.

66 **Keywords**

67 2030 Agenda; artificial intelligence technology; natural language processing;
68 interlinkage and interaction; literature review; Scopus

69

70 **1. Introduction**

71 **1.1 The 2030 Agenda at a crossroads: The need for integrated** 72 **solutions**

73 The United Nations (UN) 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was
74 adopted in 2015, and its core components, the Sustainable Development Goals
75 (SDGs), provide the compass with which we are to steer the world toward a better
76 future (United Nations 2015). Unfortunately, at the halfway mark, we are not on track
77 to accomplish the SDGs on time (Independent Group of Scientists appointed by the
78 Secretary-General 2023). Recent complex crises, including the COVID-19 pandemic,
79 increased costs of living, armed conflicts, and natural disasters, have hindered the
80 progress (Independent Group of Scientists appointed by the Secretary-General 2023).
81 The objective of sustainable development is to maximize the goals across biological,
82 economic, and social systems through an adaptive process of trade-offs (Barbier,
83 1987; Elkington, 1994; Purvis et al. 2019) and transformative actions (Pradhan 2023;
84 United Nations 2023).

85 **1.2 Understanding and mapping SDG implementations**

86 The SDGs provide a common lexicon for global stakeholders (Jun & Kim
87 2021), and several collaborative innovations by multiple actors have thus far provided
88 new ways of resolving several wicked and unruly problems complexly intertwined
89 across economic, social, and environmental challenges (United Nations 2015;
90 Hofstad & Torfing 2015; Persson et al. 2016; Mariani et al. 2022). Understanding
91 whether the multitude of actors engagement are on targets and goals and how
92 different actors collaborate to the SDGs is important to achieve the SDGs in
93 multi-level governance (Pukelis et al. 2020). An objective of the current research is to
94 provide this capability.

95 To provide the groundwork for tracking progress, several rubrics have been
96 created, including the SDG Index by the Sustainable Development Solutions Network
97 (SDSN) (Schmidt-Traub et al. 2017), Global Indicators by Inter-Agency and Expert
98 Group (United Nations Statistics Division, n.d.), and the World Development Indicator
99 by the World Bank Group (World Bank Group, n.d.). In addition to performance

100 monitoring, activities and actions monitoring of what is being done towards the
101 achievement of these goals and how these different actions fit together, is also
102 essential for fair promoting the SDGs commitment and representing the contribution
103 to the SDGs (Persson et al. 2016; Pukelis et al. 2020).

104 Based on this need, several researchers have attempted to map multiple
105 stakeholders' activities to the SDG system. In the national scale, actions stated in
106 development plan (Galsurkar et al. 2017; Jean-Baptiste et al. 2022), national budget
107 (Guariso et al. 2023), science technology and innovation policies (Hajikhani &
108 Suominen 2022), regional policies (Borchardt et al. 2023; Koundouri et al. 2022,
109 2024), United Nations documents (LaFleur 2019; Sovrano et al. 2020) are mapped on
110 the SDGs structure. In business sectors and at corporate scales, enterprise activities
111 (OECD 2021), sustainability reporting (Amel-Zadeh et al. 2021; Angin et al. 2022),
112 financial accounting policies (Li & Rockinger 2024), and social media
113 communications (ElAlfy et al. 2020; Lee & Kim 2021) were analyzed to evaluate the
114 consistency with the SDGs. In academic sectors, the curricula of many higher
115 education institutions (Lei et al. 2022; Lemarchand et al. 2023; Yao et al. 2024),
116 research and development organizations (Körfggen et al. 2018), and academic
117 attentions (Morales-Hernández et al. 2022; Wastl et al. 2020) were investigated for
118 assessing the alignment with the SDGs concepts.

119 **1.3 Detecting the SDG nexus structure**

120 The interactions or interlinkages between the Sustainable Development
121 Goals, here we call it as “the SDG nexus”, have been paid high attention. This is
122 because the efforts to achieve one specific Global Goal potentially mobilize other
123 Global Goals while hinders advancement towards other Global Goals. Untangling of
124 the complex web of interrelationships within the SDGs are often referred to as “nexus
125 approaches” (J. Liu et al. 2018). The activities of individual stakeholders should
126 strategically care the SDG nexus for avoiding trade-offs and maximally designing
127 synergetic performance (Kawakubo & Murakami 2020).

128 Early researchers focused on developing frameworks to conceptualize the
129 overall structure of the SDGs. For example, Griggs et al. (2013) proposed an
130 integrated framework in which poverty reduction and Earth's life support system were

131 twin pillars and Griggs et al. (2014) upgraded the initial framework to the six
132 candidates of the Targets. In 2016, Folke et al. (2016) and researchers at the
133 Stockholm Resilience Center (2016) introduced the “SDGs Wedding Cake” model,
134 which organizes the 17 Global Goals into a structure stratified into biospherical,
135 societal, and economical layers.

136 Following this conceptualization, the detailed SDG interactions were further
137 identified using expert judgments in the early stage (ICSU, ISSC 2015). Nilsson et al.
138 (2016) later proposed a seven-point scoring scale to classify SDG interactions, which
139 was subsequently employed in several qualitative assessments (International
140 Science Council 2017; Weitz et al. 2018; Pham-Truffert et al. 2020). In addition to
141 knowledge-based approaches, a range of quantitative methods have been applied,
142 including indicator-based statistical analysis (Pradhan et al. 2017; Kroll et al. 2019;
143 Kunčič 2019; Lusseau & Mancini 2019; Hegre et al. 2020; Warchold et al. 2021;
144 Anderson et al. 2022; Wu et al. 2022), machine learning technologies (Asadikia et al.
145 2021), and integrated assessment models (Randers et al. 2019; van Soest et al.
146 2019).

147 Although the various synergies and trade-offs among the SDGs can vary,
148 depending on the focus and context, it is generally known that synergetic interactions
149 outweigh impeding ones (Del Río Castro et al. 2021; Warchold et al. 2022). Notably,
150 certain Global Goals have been identified as having a strong potential for trade-offs.
151 For instance, Wu et al. (2022) conducted a time-series analysis and detected an
152 evolutionary interaction pattern measured by the SDG Indices and highlighted the
153 dominant influence of Goals 12 and 13 within the trade-off network. To maximize
154 cobenefits and mitigate trade-offs, knowledge coproduction is needed to fill the
155 existing gaps related to the SDG interactions (McCollum et al. 2018; Nilsson et al.
156 2018).

157 **1.4 Leveraging artificial intelligence for SDG mapping and nexus** 158 **detection**

159 Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have already been used to support
160 SDG accomplishment (Fuso Nerini et al. 2024). AI technologies are currently being

161 sought to improve the synergy and trade-offs in terms of revealing climate change
162 and the modeling of its possible impacts (Goal 13), identifying areas of poverty using
163 satellite images (Goal 1), and increasing productivity (Goal 8) while reducing
164 inequalities (Goal 10) (Vinuesa et al. 2020). In particular, large language models
165 (LLMs) have shown remarkable promise in the field of natural language processing
166 (NLP), getting attention for their potential to accelerate the progress of the SDGs
167 (Rane 2023; R. Wang et al. 2023).

168 **1.4.1 Language models for mapping SDGs**

169 SDG classifiers have been developed to map policy documents and reports
170 to relevant Global Goals and Targets. In early efforts, keyword lists associated with
171 each Global Goal and Target were developed deductively and classify texts
172 according to these lists, which is known as rule-based classification systems.
173 Representative examples include a listing developed by SDSN Australia/Pacific
174 (2017) that is used to classify university contributions to the SDGs and a query set
175 created by Elsevier that apportions academic publications to Global Goals
176 (Jayabalasingham et al. 2019; Rivest et al. 2021; Roberge et al. 2022; Bedard-Vallee
177 et al. 2023). Numerous other studies have employed similar keyword-based
178 approaches (Bautista-Puig & Mauleón 2019; Duran-Silva et al. 2019; Armitage et al.
179 2020; Pukelis et al. 2020;).

180 Unfortunately, rule-based classification method suffers from several
181 limitations, including researcher subjectivity (Armitage et al. 2020) and an inability to
182 account for detailed contexts and semantics (Jean-Baptiste et al. 2022; Yin et al.
183 2023b). To overcome these limitations, machine learning-based SDG classifiers have
184 been increasingly developed. For example, supervised learning techniques with
185 feature-based models (e.g., support vector machines, and naïve Bayes models) have
186 been used on datasets containing manually labeled texts and abstracts of scientific
187 publications retrieved using SDG-related queries (Pincet et al. 2019; Amel-Zadeh et
188 al. 2021; OECD 2021; Hajikhani & Suominen 2022; Lei et al. 2022;
189 Morales-Hernández et al. 2022; Pukelis et al. 2022). Unsupervised learning
190 approaches (e.g., latent Dirichlet allocation) have also been explored (Galsurkar et al.
191 2017; LaFleur 2019; Sovrano et al. 2020; Hsu et al. 2022).

192 Within the machine learning algorithms, especially the transformer
193 architecture is a deep learning algorithm developed by Vaswani et al. (2017), and the
194 Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) model was created
195 by Devlin et al. (2019). These tools have revolutionized the NLP field, demonstrating
196 very high performance and accuracy across a variety of NLP tasks and leading to
197 advanced SDG classifiers (Dialogic 2021, 2024; Angin et al. 2022; Guisiano et al.
198 2022; Jean-Baptiste et al. 2022; Matsui et al. 2022; Morales-Hernández et al. 2022;
199 Vanderfeesten et al. 2022; Koundouri et al. 2024; Li & Rockinger 2024). More
200 recently, the use of Generative Pre-trained Transformers (GPTs) has resulted in
201 excellent text generations (Radford et al. 2018). These are also now being applied to
202 SDG classification tasks (La Fleur 2023; Sashida et al. 2023; Yin et al. 2023a;
203 Kharlashkin et al. 2024).

204 **1.4.2 Language models for detecting SDG nexus**

205 NLP technologies have greatly improved in their ability to detect semantic
206 linkages among the SDGs. Early work in this area (Le Blanc 2015) investigated the
207 Target relationships based on their wording. Subsequent research (Smith et al. 2021)
208 utilized the machine learning techniques to overcome researcher bias in qualitative
209 approaches and the data limitations of quantitative analyses. Smith et al. (2021)
210 employed doc2vec (Le & Mikolov 2014), an algorithm that converts documents to
211 embedded vectors, enabling semantic comparisons among the description of Global
212 Goals. Bellantuono et al. (2022) leveraged word2vec (Mikolov et al. 2013), a similar
213 algorithm with doc2vec, to construct semantic networks of the 17 Global Goals, and
214 compared them to the result of the correlation analysis that use SDG indicators.
215 Similarly, Song and Jang (2023) used word2vec to analyze relationships among
216 Targets and identified priorities based on network centralities. Our team has notably
217 explored the SDG nexus utilizing BERT, which offers a highly nuanced understanding
218 of semantics (Matsui et al. 2022).

219 **1.5 Research gap and questions**

220 Thus, powerful support tools that translate stakeholder activities into a
221 structured understanding of SDG interlinkages are needed to facilitate collaborative
222 innovations, which are crucial to accelerating the progress of the 2030 Agenda.

223 However, a key challenge remains: the interpretive diversity of the SDGs. The
224 language used to describe SDG-related activities varies significantly across sectors
225 from policy documents and academic papers to corporate reports and civil society
226 initiatives. This diversity poses a significant hurdle for developing truly generalizable
227 classifiers.

228 Many prior multi-label SDG classifiers, including the excellent work by
229 Guisiano et al. (2022), have relied on relatively homogenous data sources. We argue
230 that this approach can lead to models overfitting to the specific phrasings and
231 contexts of a single sector, thereby failing to capture the universal and multifaceted
232 nature of the SDGs. While some studies, such as Jean-Baptiste et al. (2022), have
233 utilized multiple data sources, these were primarily from official and international
234 bodies. Furthermore, the methodological implications and effectiveness of this
235 diverse-sourcing approach were not a central part of their investigation. We therefore
236 identify a critical research gap in addressing this challenge of interpretive diversity
237 through a deliberate and methodologically-grounded approach.

238 Our primary conceptual contribution is to propose and quantitatively
239 demonstrate an approach we term “Cross-Sectoral Semantic Generalization” to
240 address this gap. To achieve this, we intentionally designed a novel heterogeneous
241 and multi-sectoral training corpus that includes not only official documents but also
242 local-level and civil-sector data. By directly exposing the model to these diverse
243 interpretations, we hypothesize that it can learn more robust and generalizable
244 representations of the SDGs. Therefore, our core conceptual contribution is a
245 methodological one: we provide new empirical evidence on how intentionally
246 maximizing the diversity of training sources improves a classifier’s generalization
247 performance on unseen external data.

248 Accordingly, we have identified three research questions (RQ) that will be
249 answered by the current study.

250 RQ 1: How generalizable are multi-label text classification models that are
251 trained on diverse datasets when translating text semantics into Global Goals?

252 RQ 2: Can the trained model detect which Global Goals and Targets are most

253 and least addressed by scientific articles?

254 RQ 3: Can the trained model infer the seeds of innovations by analyzing the
255 structure of the SDG nexus within the scientific attention?

256

2. Materials and methods

Fig. 1 Pipeline for developing language models and detecting the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) nexus.

258

259 The pipeline for developing the language models for detecting the SDG nexus
 260 hidden in scientific articles is shown in Fig. 1. The pipeline consists of four steps; (1)
 261 constructing the corpus for model training; (2) training the models with optimizing the
 262 hyperparameters; (3) evaluating the generalization performance on the external
 263 dataset; (4) assessing the nexus in the scientific articles of sustainable development.
 264 The detail each step is described below.

265 2.1 Building the training corpus

266

Table 1 Summary of the training corpus

Source	Number of documents	Token per document	Goal 01	Goal 02	Goal 03	Goal 04	Goal 05	Goal 06	Goal 07	Goal 08	Goal 09	Goal 10	Goal 11	Goal 12	Goal 13	Goal 14	Goal 15	Goal 16	Goal 17	Labels per document
01 SDGs Definition	434	20	21	23	42	23	24	20	12	29	21	25	26	25	14	21	27	37	44	1.0
02 UN SDGs Progress	1,180	71	55	64	134	65	74	69	48	76	72	56	52	48	43	50	70	92	112	1.0
03 SDG Actions Platform	7,480	492	1,463	1,401	1,309	1,844	1,687	1,844	1,065	1,967	1,068	1,009	1,252	1,660	2,193	3,065	1,341	1,058	2,257	3.7
04 SDG Knowledge Hub	7,607	589	1,589	1,631	1,780	986	1,462	1,381	1,678	1,759	1,616	1,622	1,414	1,592	3,466	1,481	1,977	1,606	3,932	4.1
05 Japanese Cabinet	850	72	96	149	169	137	110	97	124	250	291	71	200	168	256	126	126	105	168	3.1
06 Plastics Smart	3,454	102	69	43	239	185	94	218	231	254	430	67	1,008	2,536	685	2,656	670	70	979	3.0
07 PANCES	153	31	0	66	79	5	0	33	42	74	79	6	37	88	86	64	84	0	35	5.1
08 Zenoku Net	467	166	7	18	18	107	6	9	131	20	63	8	165	63	278	37	67	5	103	2.4
09 EXPO	1,591	412	66	49	404	478	112	25	71	343	231	193	542	332	180	160	172	132	672	2.6
10 Osaka University	683	354	51	58	431	88	42	52	209	78	382	82	115	112	119	66	78	47	64	3.0
11 Hokkaido University	70	192	4	9	25	14	7	5	6	11	16	9	26	13	23	22	28	9	24	3.6
Total	23,969	403	3,421	3,511	4,630	3,932	3,618	3,753	3,617	4,861	4,269	3,148	4,837	6,637	7,343	7,748	4,640	3,161	8,390	3.4
Token per document			617	589	531	530	605	552	535	526	493	634	472	376	518	323	492	608	521	

267

268 Our training corpus for SDG translation was constructed by appending texts
269 explicitly linked to the Global Goals from diverse government, academia, industry,
270 and civil sources. A detailed overview of sources is summarized in Table 1. The “01
271 SDGs Definition” source comprises the official definitions of the 17 Global Goals and
272 169 Targets from the 2030 Agenda (United Nations 2015) and their 231 unique global
273 indicators (United Nations Statistics Division, n.d.). The “02 UN SDGs Progress”
274 source consists of paragraphs extracted from annual “Progress towards the
275 Sustainable Development Goals” reports published by the UN from 2016 to 2023
276 (United Nations 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023). Both sources are
277 single-labeled in English. The “03 SDG Actions Platform” source includes documents
278 registered on the UN SDG Actions Platform, where various stakeholders (e.g.,
279 governments, NGOs, civil society organizations, businesses, and partnerships) post
280 and share their SDG-related activities (United Nations, n.d.). The “04 SDG
281 Knowledge Hub” source comprises news articles associated with SDGs compiled by
282 the International Institute for Sustainable Development and loaded to the SDG
283 Knowledge Hub (IISD, n.d.). Both sources are multi-labeled in English.

284 In addition to these English corpora, several Japanese sources, whose quality
285 can be carefully investigated in authors’ native language, were combined. From the
286 public sector, the “05 Japanese Cabinet” was taken from the SDGs Action Plan of the
287 Cabinet Office of Japan (Prime Minister’s Office of Japan, n.d.). The “06 Plastics
288 Smart” source, which addresses plastic pollution problems identified by diverse
289 stakeholders, is registered by Ministry of the Environment Government of Japan (n.d.),
290 and the “07 PANCES” source comprises a list of biodiversity and ecosystem
291 conservation policies (National Institute for Environmental Studies, n.d.).

292 Regarding private and industrial sectors, the “08 Zenkoku Net” source consists
293 of decarbonization effort documents stored by the Japan Network for Climate Change
294 (Actions, n.d.), and the “09 EXPO” source comprises the SDG-related actions of the
295 participants in the special initiative for the 2025 World Exposition in Osaka, Japan
296 (Japan Association for the 2025 World Exposition, n.d.). As for the academic sector,
297 we gathered the SDG-related research and educational activities of Osaka University
298 (our university) and Hokkaido University (top rank SDGs contributor in Japanese

299 universities) as items “10” and “11,” respectively (Hokkaido University, 2020; Osaka
300 University 2024). All Japanese corpora are multi-labeled and their sentences were
301 translated into English using Google Translator via the Python deep-translator library
302 (Baccouri 2020/2024).

303 All texts were preprocessed using Normalization Form Compatibility
304 Composition (Python, n.d.), and extraneous whitespace was removed. The final
305 training corpus comprised 23,969 documents. The most frequent Global Goals
306 included Goal 17 (Partnerships for the Goals), Goal 15 (Life Below Water), and Goal
307 13 (Climate Action), and the least frequent were Goal 10 (Reduced Inequalities) and
308 Goal 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions). The training corpus exhibited a
309 maximum 2.7-fold difference in the number of documents associated with each
310 Global Goal, and the number of tokens per document varied substantially across
311 sources, which ensured diversity of text length. The mean of tokens per document
312 across all Global Goals was 525 (SD = 79), indicating a relatively consistent text
313 lengths within each Global Goal. The number of labels per document ranged from
314 one to five, with an average of 3.4.

315 **2.1.1 Label Consistency Validation**

316 The labels in our heterogeneous training corpus, which were self-declared by
317 the originating entities, require a quantitative assessment of their validity. To address
318 this, we conducted a label consistency validation study. We randomly sampled 110
319 documents (10 from each of our 11 sources) from the final training corpus. One of the
320 authors, serving as a domain expert on the SDGs, re-labeled these documents for all
321 17 Goals under blind conditions (i.e., without reference to the original, self-declared
322 labels). Using the expert's annotations as the ground truth, we evaluated the quality
323 of the original labels in the sample. The macro-averaged F1-score across all SDGs
324 was 0.57 (Precision: 0.44, Recall: 0.82), confirming that the self-declared labels
325 possess a reasonable degree of validity from an objective standpoint, particularly in
326 terms of recall. This suggests that while the original labels may sometimes be overly
327 broad (lower precision), they generally succeed in capturing the relevant SDG themes
328 (higher recall). As a supplementary analysis, we also tasked two leading large
329 language models (LLMs), GPT-4o and Gemini-2.5-flash, with the same multi-label

330 classification task on the sampled documents. The overall agreement among the
331 human expert and the two LLMs was also assessed. The full details of this
332 comprehensive validation are provided in the Supplementary Information (Section
333 S1).

334 **2.2 Model selection**

335 The training corpus was applied to the training of three different
336 Transformer-based language models; Robustly optimized BERT approach
337 (RoBERTa), Decoding-enhanced BERT with disentangled attention (DeBERTa); and
338 Language Understanding with Knowledge-based Embeddings (LUKE). BERT is the
339 basis of these models and was pre-trained on two tasks: Masked Language Model
340 (MLM), where the model predicts masked tokens by referring to the surrounding
341 context, and next sentence prediction, where the model predicts whether two given
342 sentences are sequential (Devlin et al. 2019). This pre-training enables BERT to learn
343 rich contextual representations of language, resulting in strong performance on a
344 wide range of NLP tasks. RoBERTa improves upon the BERT by consuming a larger
345 training dataset and utilizing dynamic masking in MLM (Y. Liu et al. 2019). DeBERTa
346 incorporates a disentangled attention mechanism, which encodes the content and
347 position of inputs separately, and an enhanced mask decoder that leverages absolute
348 position information during MLM (He et al. 2021). DeBERTaV3 is an improved
349 version of DeBERTa (He et al. 2023). LUKE builds upon RoBERTa with an
350 entity-aware architecture, which excels in knowledge-intensive downstream tasks
351 (Yamada et al. 2020). We fine-tuned “roberta-large” (Hugging Face, n.d.-b),
352 “microsoft/deberta-v3-large” (microsoft, n.d.), and “studio-ousia/luke-large-lite”
353 (studio-ousia, n.d.). These models are available through Hugging Face (Hugging
354 Face 2024). We then compared the performance results of these models, which we
355 report on later.

356 **2.3 Classifier architecture**

357 The three base models share a common transformer architecture that takes
358 512 text tokens as input and processes them through 24 encoder layers, producing
359 1,024-dimensional embedding vectors for each token. These are then passed
360 through an average pooling layer that averages all token embedding vectors except

padding tokens. The averaged vector is then fed into a 17-dimensional classification layer that predicts the relevance of each of the 17 Global Goals. Dropout is applied to both the average pooling and classification layers to avoid overfitting and enhance generalization performance.

2.4 Optimizing, training, and evaluating processes

The training corpus was split into training (60%), validation (20%), and test (20%) sets. Stratified sampling was performed using the `MultilabelStratifiedKFold` class (*Iterative-Stratification*, n.d.; Sechidis et al. 2011) to minimize the differences in label distributions across splits. The AdamW (Loshchilov & Hutter 2019) and linear scheduler with warmup (Hugging Face, n.d.-a) were used as for optimizer and learning rate adjustments, respectively, during training. The loss function was BinaryCrossEntropy (PyTorch, n.d.) with class weights inversely proportional to the number of samples per label. Label smoothing (Szegedy et al. 2016) was employed to further enhance generalizability, and automatic mixed precision (NVIDIA Developer, n.d.) was used to accelerate training.

Seven hyperparameters were optimized using Optuna (Akiba et al. 2019): the number of trainable encoder layers (1–10), encoder, pooling, and classification layer learning rate, ($1e-5$ – $1e-3$), pooling and classification layer dropout rate (0.0–0.5), and batch size (4–32). Hyperparameter optimization was performed over 128 trials using the Bayesian optimization algorithm to maximize the F1-score of the validation set after 16 epochs of training. The HyperbandPruner algorithm (Akiba et al. 2019) was used to terminate unpromising trials early.

Using these optimized hyperparameters, the test models were trained on the combined training and validation sets (80% of the corpus), and their performance was evaluated on a held-out test set (20%). The predicted probabilities were binarized using a cutoff of 0.5, and we used evaluation metrics of precision, recall, and F1-score (the harmonic mean of the precision and recall). The best models were trained on the entire training corpus and applied to the generalization evaluation and analysis of scientific articles.

390 **2.5 Generalization performance**

391 To assess the generalizability of our models, we evaluated their performance
392 on two distinct external datasets: the OSDG Community Dataset (OSDG-CD) (OSDG
393 et al. 2024) and the SDG Integration Corpus (SDGi Corpus) (Skrynnyk et al. 2024).

394 The OSDG-CD consists of 43,025 single-labeled texts derived from reports,
395 policy documents, and publications, with label quality validated by at least three
396 volunteers. For our evaluation, we used a highly verified subset of 15,738 texts where
397 all volunteers agreed on the label. The SDGi Corpus is a multilingual, multi-label
398 dataset created by UNDP researchers from Voluntary National Reviews (VNRs) and
399 Voluntary Local Reviews (VLRs). It contains a total of 7,350 texts in English, Spanish,
400 and French; we used only the English texts (n=5,282) for this study. Although the
401 SDGi Corpus is multi-labeled, we note that the majority of its entries (88.9%) are
402 single-labeled.

403 A key challenge in evaluating our multi-label models on these predominantly
404 single-labeled datasets is that the precision metric can be misleading. If a model
405 correctly identifies other contextually relevant SDGs in addition to the single provided
406 label, these correct predictions are unfairly penalized as "False Positives,"
407 systematically deflating the precision score. Recall, on the other hand, is robust to this
408 issue as it simply measures whether the model successfully identified the single true
409 label provided. Therefore, we consider recall a much fairer and more reliable indicator
410 of a model's fundamental classification capability on these external datasets.

411 **2.6 Utility evaluation**

412 To evaluate the utility of the multi-label text classification model for mapping
413 texts to the SDGs and detecting a nexus, we applied the best model to scientific
414 articles. First, we retrieved 161,520 scientific articles written in English recorded in the
415 Scopus (Scopus, n.d.) in August 2024, in which titles, abstracts, or keywords
416 contained the phrase "sustainable development." We then predicted the relevant
417 Global Goals for each article in a binary multi-label format by inputting the
418 concatenated text of title, abstract, and keywords into the best model. We assessed
419 the relevant Targets of each article by calculating the cosine similarity between the

420 17-dimensional predicted probability vectors of the article text and the Target
421 definition. Based on this similarity score, we established connections between texts
422 and Targets to construct a co-occurrence network. We then calculated the Jaccard
423 similarity coefficient of each pair of Global Goal and Target. This Jaccard similarity
424 coefficient represents the proportion of articles assigned to both Global Goals /
425 Targets out of all articles assigned to either Global Goals / Targets in the pair. Finally,
426 we constructed and analyzed the networks of Global Goals and Targets based on
427 these Jaccard similarity coefficients to explore the characteristics of the SDG and
428 Target nexuses in the scientific attention.

429 The threshold for establishing these connections is a critical parameter.
430 Therefore, we conducted a dedicated analysis to justify our choice of the 0.8 cosine
431 similarity threshold. We varied the threshold from 0.1 to 0.9 and calculated the
432 modularity—a measure of community structure quality—of the resulting Target
433 co-occurrence network for each value. While modularity peaked at a threshold of 0.9,
434 a qualitative review of the network structures revealed that this value led to an overly
435 fragmented network that obscured inter-goal relationships. The 0.8 threshold was
436 selected as it provides an optimal balance between achieving high modularity and
437 ensuring the scientific interpretability of the nexus structure. The full details of this
438 data-driven threshold optimization are provided in the Supplementary Information
439 (Section S2).

440

441 3. Results

442 3.1 Multi-label classification performance

Table 2 Optimized hyperparameters

	RoBERTa	DeBERTa	LUKE
Batch size	18	29	25
Learning rate of encoder layers	2.35×10^{-5}	7.37×10^{-5}	3.66×10^{-5}
Learning rate of pooling layer	1.32×10^{-5}	2.92×10^{-4}	8.79×10^{-5}
Learning rate of classification layer	2.56×10^{-5}	6.48×10^{-5}	1.06×10^{-5}
Dropout rate of pooling layer	0.36	0.43	0.26
Dropout rate of classification layer	0.06	0.35	0.12
Number of trainable encoder layers	10	9	10

443

444 The optimized hyperparameters of the three models are listed in Table 2. The
445 bayesian optimization found the best hyperparameters after 44 trials for RoBERTa,
446 27 trials for DeBERTa, and 47 trials for LUKE.

447

Table 3 Classification performance on the test set

	RoBERTa			DeBERTa			LUKE			Support
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score	
Goal 01	0.555	0.624	0.588	0.572	0.618	0.594	0.573	0.646	0.607	684
Goal 02	0.649	0.661	0.655	0.642	0.654	0.648	0.646	0.688	0.666	702
Goal 03	0.684	0.684	0.684	0.708	0.692	0.700	0.666	0.680	0.673	926
Goal 04	0.681	0.659	0.670	0.690	0.682	0.686	0.673	0.670	0.672	786
Goal 05	0.628	0.637	0.632	0.645	0.656	0.650	0.643	0.634	0.638	724
Goal 06	0.727	0.668	0.696	0.722	0.671	0.695	0.723	0.692	0.707	750
Goal 07	0.656	0.665	0.661	0.674	0.658	0.666	0.649	0.679	0.664	723
Goal 08	0.636	0.646	0.641	0.650	0.652	0.651	0.642	0.655	0.649	972
Goal 09	0.575	0.537	0.555	0.577	0.566	0.572	0.584	0.567	0.576	853
Goal 10	0.516	0.637	0.570	0.558	0.641	0.597	0.521	0.637	0.573	630
Goal 11	0.601	0.616	0.608	0.621	0.620	0.621	0.605	0.628	0.616	967
Goal 12	0.741	0.716	0.728	0.752	0.703	0.727	0.738	0.715	0.727	1,328
Goal 13	0.745	0.698	0.721	0.751	0.702	0.726	0.753	0.695	0.723	1,469
Goal 14	0.858	0.826	0.841	0.835	0.830	0.832	0.843	0.828	0.835	1,549
Goal 15	0.651	0.614	0.632	0.639	0.631	0.635	0.629	0.642	0.635	928
Goal 16	0.619	0.606	0.612	0.637	0.639	0.638	0.591	0.630	0.610	632
Goal 17	0.703	0.613	0.655	0.679	0.660	0.669	0.717	0.631	0.671	1,678
Micro avg.	0.676	0.663	0.669	0.681	0.674	0.678	0.674	0.674	0.674	16,301
Macro avg.	0.660	0.653	0.656	0.668	0.663	0.665	0.658	0.666	0.661	
Weighted avg.	0.679	0.663	0.670	0.684	0.674	0.678	0.678	0.674	0.675	
Samples avg.	0.744	0.747	0.695	0.744	0.758	0.702	0.742	0.753	0.699	

448

449 Table 3 presents the classification performance on the best model’s test set.
450 According to the micro average F1-score, DeBERTa achieved the highest
451 performance (0.678), followed by LUKE (0.674) and RoBERTa (0.669). Across all
452 models, Goal 14 (Life Below Water) exhibited high F1-scores (>0.83), whereas Goal
453 09 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure) and Goal 10 (Reduced Inequalities)
454 consistently had lower F1-scores (<0.6). This variation in performance between the
455 three models was generally less than 10%, whereas the variation across the Global
456 Goals was approximately 30%, which is greater than the model differences. For
457 Goals 04, 06, 09, 12, 13, 14, and 17, the precision was consistently high across all
458 models, indicating that false positive of these Global Goals were relatively low and
459 unlikely to be misclassified. However, for Goals 01, 02, 08, and 10, recall was
460 generally high, suggesting that the models avert false negatives and the overlooking
461 risks.

462

463 **3.2 Generalization performance**

464

Table 4 Classification performance on the External Dataset

a) Classification Performance on OSDG-CD

	RoBERTa			DeBERTa			LUKE			Support
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score	
Goal 01	0.569	0.811	0.669	0.572	0.504	0.535	0.581	0.798	0.672	840
Goal 02	0.699	0.746	0.722	0.567	0.440	0.496	0.705	0.734	0.719	661
Goal 03	0.866	0.893	0.879	0.788	0.611	0.688	0.844	0.912	0.876	1,470
Goal 04	0.826	0.928	0.874	0.820	0.525	0.640	0.814	0.927	0.867	1,694
Goal 05	0.850	0.814	0.832	0.870	0.534	0.661	0.851	0.789	0.819	1,904
Goal 06	0.910	0.801	0.852	0.892	0.484	0.627	0.908	0.803	0.852	1,226
Goal 07	0.870	0.851	0.860	0.864	0.522	0.651	0.860	0.868	0.864	1,279
Goal 08	0.362	0.679	0.473	0.249	0.444	0.319	0.327	0.721	0.450	702
Goal 09	0.595	0.676	0.633	0.443	0.521	0.479	0.569	0.718	0.635	823
Goal 10	0.352	0.651	0.457	0.223	0.450	0.298	0.320	0.655	0.430	487
Goal 11	0.774	0.791	0.782	0.670	0.494	0.569	0.734	0.804	0.768	965
Goal 12	0.351	0.814	0.491	0.310	0.503	0.384	0.262	0.856	0.401	167
Goal 13	0.760	0.838	0.797	0.614	0.530	0.569	0.682	0.823	0.746	757
Goal 14	0.849	0.936	0.890	0.777	0.567	0.655	0.778	0.946	0.854	607
Goal 15	0.782	0.924	0.847	0.677	0.596	0.634	0.777	0.924	0.844	581
Goal 16	0.858	0.881	0.869	0.764	0.560	0.646	0.826	0.909	0.865	1,575
Micro avg.	0.733	0.829	0.778	0.635	0.526	0.575	0.702	0.836	0.763	15,738
Macro avg.	0.705	0.815	0.745	0.631	0.518	0.553	0.677	0.824	0.729	
Weighted avg.	0.767	0.829	0.791	0.708	0.526	0.593	0.747	0.836	0.781	
Samples avg.	0.761	0.829	0.783	0.472	0.526	0.489	0.753	0.836	0.779	

465 b) Classification Performance on SDGi-Corpus

	RoBERTa			DeBERTa			LUKE			Support
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score	
Goal 01	0.303	0.833	0.445	0.406	0.821	0.544	0.299	0.818	0.438	407
Goal 02	0.492	0.864	0.627	0.487	0.864	0.623	0.503	0.853	0.633	353
Goal 03	0.600	0.758	0.670	0.582	0.764	0.661	0.634	0.727	0.677	501
Goal 04	0.547	0.811	0.654	0.567	0.836	0.676	0.552	0.809	0.656	477
Goal 05	0.342	0.869	0.491	0.412	0.863	0.558	0.293	0.853	0.436	388
Goal 06	0.488	0.834	0.616	0.479	0.865	0.616	0.581	0.837	0.686	326
Goal 07	0.448	0.859	0.589	0.554	0.876	0.679	0.441	0.870	0.585	347
Goal 08	0.477	0.739	0.580	0.454	0.799	0.579	0.395	0.747	0.517	522
Goal 09	0.534	0.706	0.608	0.536	0.728	0.618	0.498	0.681	0.575	445
Goal 10	0.509	0.717	0.595	0.445	0.778	0.566	0.389	0.732	0.508	459
Goal 11	0.468	0.838	0.601	0.433	0.836	0.571	0.482	0.827	0.609	641
Goal 12	0.588	0.811	0.681	0.507	0.823	0.628	0.520	0.794	0.629	417
Goal 13	0.559	0.714	0.627	0.493	0.753	0.596	0.477	0.753	0.584	490
Goal 14	0.624	0.866	0.725	0.631	0.874	0.733	0.725	0.836	0.777	262
Goal 15	0.636	0.842	0.724	0.608	0.859	0.712	0.636	0.807	0.711	348
Goal 16	0.516	0.787	0.623	0.606	0.778	0.681	0.429	0.773	0.552	418
Goal 17	0.585	0.604	0.594	0.468	0.675	0.553	0.684	0.556	0.613	538
Micro avg.	0.491	0.783	0.604	0.496	0.804	0.613	0.466	0.773	0.581	7,339
Macro avg.	0.513	0.791	0.615	0.510	0.811	0.623	0.502	0.781	0.599	
Weighted avg.	0.512	0.783	0.612	0.504	0.804	0.617	0.499	0.773	0.594	
Samples avg.	0.692	0.913	0.730	0.684	0.923	0.731	0.667	0.910	0.709	

466

467

468 The generalization performance of the models was evaluated on two external
469 datasets, OSDG-CD and SDGi Corpus, with the results detailed in Table 4. First, on
470 our internal test set (Table 3), the difference in F1-scores between the top models
471 was negligible (DeBERTa: 0.678 vs. LUKE: 0.674). Given this similarity, we argue
472 that a model's true value lies in its generalization to unseen external data, which we
473 prioritized in our selection. As justified in Section 2.5, recall is the most reliable metric
474 for evaluating our multi-label models on the predominantly single-labeled external
475 datasets. On the OSDG-CD in Table 4 a), LUKE's recall (0.836) was overwhelmingly
476 superior to DeBERTa's (0.526). On the SDGi Corpus in Table 4 b), DeBERTa
477 exhibited a higher recall than LUKE.

478 To make a final decision, we conducted an integrated assessment based on
479 the combined performance across both external datasets. We calculated the average
480 recall for each model across both OSDG-CD and SDGi Corpus. In this
481 comprehensive evaluation, LUKE achieved the highest average LUKE recall of 0.816,
482 followed closely by RoBERTa at 0.815, while DeBERTa's was significantly lower at

490 To validate whether the best model captured the most important concepts of
 491 each Global Goal, we extracted the most relevant words by Global Goals by summing
 492 their attention weights. Fig. 2 visualizes these words as word clouds. First, we
 493 mapped all texts within the OSDG-CD to each Global Goal. Then, we applied the
 494 word cloud visualization. For example, highly relevant poverty issues (e.g., “poor” and
 495 “deprivation”) are well represented in the word cloud of Goal 01. “Investment” and
 496 “business” are pertinent within Goal 09.

497

Fig. 3 Distribution of Global Goals predicted by the best model. Each distribution represents the distribution of predicted labels by the model for texts with true labels included in OSDG-CD. For example, the predicted distribution for the texts labeled as Goal 10 in OSDG-CD often has a peak in Goal 10 itself. However, Goals 01 and 08 were also predicted, indicating that Goals 01, 08, and 10 have shared semantics.

498

499 We further examined the classification tendencies of the best model using
 500 OSDG-CD. Fig. 3 provides the distribution of predicted labels to texts in the
 501 OSDG-CD. Overall, the distributions of predicted Goals were concentrated to true
 502 labels, which is reflected by the best model's recall performance in Table 4. Notably,
 503 the best model additionally predicted Goal 08 (Decent Work and Economic Growth)
 504 to the texts truly labeled as Goals 01, 05, and 10. Inductively, this indicates that
 505 poverty may be improved by macroeconomic policies and by reducing disparities
 506 between gender and that inequalities can be mitigated by the proliferation of decent
 507 works (ICSU, ISSC 2015).

508 3.4 Inferred scientific attention to Global Goals and Targets

509

Fig. 4 Distribution of scientific attention to each Global Goal. The bar size shows the number of scientific articles labeled as each Global Goal by the best model. The percentage indicates the proportion of them to the total number of scientific articles (n=161,520).

510

511 We analyzed the collected scientific articles using the best model to identify

512 the distribution of scientific attention across SDGs. As shown in Fig. 4, the largest
 513 number of articles were mapped to Goal 12 (30.5%), followed by Goal 09 (28.5%)
 514 and Goal 07 (27.9%). Comparatively fewer articles were mapped to Goals 05, 10, and
 515 16, which focus on equity, equality, and justice, and Goals 01 and 04, which focus on
 516 basic human rights. These results imply a concentration of scientific attention on
 517 environmental sustainability and a comparatively sparse focus on social sustainability.
 518 This tendency aligns with the findings of (Asatani et al. 2020; Mishra et al. 2024;
 519 Sianes et al. 2022; Yamaguchi et al. 2023; Yeh et al. 2022).

520

Fig. 5 Time-series change of scientific attention from 2000 to 2023. Each line shows the number of scientific articles labeled as each Global Goal by the best model.

521

522 Fig. 5 presents the time-series trends of the number of scientific articles
 523 mapped to each Global Goal from 2000 to 2023. Over time, the number of articles
 524 increases across all Global Goals, reflecting a growing research interest. This
 525 supports the findings of current bibliographic analyses (Meschede 2020; Mishra et al.
 526 2024). However, the rate of increase varies among the Global Goals. Although the

527 scientific articles mapped to Goals 09, 12, 13, and 07 (related to circular economy
528 and climate change) exponentially increase, those mapped to Goals 05, 16, and 10
529 (equality and justice) showed a more gradual increase. This may indicate that an
530 imbalance of scientific attention among the Global Goals can be accelerated.

531 **3.4 Nexus detection of Global Goals in sustainability articles**

Fig. 6. Chord diagram of co-occurrences of scientific attention to each Global Goal. Each segment on the circumference corresponds to each Global Goals in clockwise order. The scale on the outer edge of each segment represents the co-occurrence frequency. The width of the arc between two segments indicates the co-occurrence frequency.

532

533 To investigate the nexus structure inherent in the scientific articles, we
534 analyzed the co-occurrence of predicted Global Goals and Targets. Each article was
535 multi-labeled by the best model. Hence, we counted the number of co-occurrences
536 between Global Goals in scientific attention and grasp the absolute volume of
537 scientific attention. Fig. 6 presents a chord diagram visualizing the co-occurrence
538 relationships. On average, each scientific article was estimated to be associated with
539 2.59 (SD = 1.88) Global Goals. The most frequent co-occurring pair was Goals 12
540 and 09. This result likely reflects a strong interdependency between infrastructure
541 development and consumption and production patterns, as noted by ICSU and ISSC
542 (2015).

543

Fig. 7 Network of Global Goals in scientific attention. The node sizes are proportional to the number of scientific articles labeled by the best model, and the edge widths are proportional to the Jaccard similarity coefficient between Global Goals. The dashed line divides the nodes into two clusters by the modularity optimization algorithm; Social Cluster (Goals 01, 03, 04, 05, 08, 10, 16, and 17) and Environmental Cluster (Goals 02, 06, 07, 09, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15).

544

545 The similarities between the Global Goals were visualized as the network in
546 Fig. 7. By using multi-labeled data frame, we calculated the Jaccard similarity
547 coefficient, which reflects the relative volume of scientific articles. Using a modularity
548 optimization algorithm (Clauset et al. 2004), the network was divided into two
549 clusters: one socially focused on ending poverty and reducing discrimination and
550 inequality and the other focused on environmental challenges related to biodiversity
551 conservation, climate action, and resource efficiency. The illustration suggests that
552 the interconnections are strong within each cluster. From this, a disconnect between
553 environmental and social sustainability research is observed.

554 We further analyzed the betweenness centrality of the Global Goals in the
555 network. This metric reflects the frequency of node locations along the shortest paths
556 between nodes. Thus, a high betweenness centrality indicates a high influence on
557 other Global Goals. Goal 01 exhibited the highest betweenness centrality (10%),
558 followed by Goal 08 (8.3%) and Goal 03 (5.8%). Although these Global Goals reflect
559 a moderate number of associated scientific articles (Fig. 4), their influences are
560 greater than that of the others. Indeed, poverty eradication and economic growth are
561 been core issues according to the Brundtland Report entitled “Our Common Future”
562 (United Nations, 1987), which prioritizes alleviating world poverty. Health remains the
563 central interest within the SDGs (Buse & Hawkes 2015). The COVID-19 pandemic
564 highlights the concept of “One Health,” the Interconnectedness of Human, Animal,
565 and Ecosystem (Adisasmito et al. 2022). In addition, these Global Goals are
566 frequently located in the shortest paths to Goal 05 (Gender Equality) or Goal 10
567 (Reduced Inequalities), which tend to be marginalized in the sustainability research
568 (Yamaguchi et al. 2023). These Global Goals could serve as entry points to leverage
569 the SDG nexus.

570 **3.5 Nexus detection of Targets in sustainability articles**

571

Fig. 8 Dendrogram illustrating the hierarchical clustering of Targets based on their Jaccard similarity coefficient in the scientific articles. The percentage after each Target label represents the proportion of scientific articles mapped to the Target to the total number of articles (n=161,520). The colored arcs represent distinct communities of Targets extracted by the modularity optimization algorithm.

572

573

Fig. 8 presents the results of clustering the target co-occurrence network based on the Jaccard similarity coefficient. The distribution of scientific articles across the predicted Targets largely mirrors that observed with the Global Goals. Although Targets belonging to the same Global Goal are found within the same community, the dendrogram reveals more nuanced relationships. For example, Community 2, which

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577

578 comprises Targets from Goal 05 (Gender Equality), 10 (Reduced Inequalities), and
579 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions), reflects the theme of social inclusion
580 central to the “Leave No One Behind” principle (Stuart & Samman 2017). Community
581 4, which represents basic human needs (Goals 01 and 02) is adjacent to Community
582 3, which comprises Targets related to economic growth and the availability of decent
583 work (Goal 8). This reflects the SDG considers the economic development essentially
584 connects with poverty eradication (Lim et al. 2018). Community 7, the largest,
585 encompasses themes related to renewable energy technologies for climate change
586 mitigation, innovation for resource efficiency, and urban infrastructure development
587 for climate change adaptation, underscoring the strong connection between
588 technological advancements and climate action. These cohesive relationships
589 between Targets embedded within scientific articles offer valuable insights for the
590 integrated research and development of SDGs. The SDGs are often criticized for
591 being too complex due to too many Global Goals and Targets, posing the challenges
592 to grasp the overall picture. When considering new goals to be set in the post-2030
593 agenda, the consolidation and abolishment of some Global Goals and Targets may
594 be considered. The results of this study can contribute to such future discussions.

595

596 **4. Discussion**

597 **4.1 Technical SDG classifier issues**

598 We developed a highly generalizable multi-label text classification model to
599 map stakeholder activities into a structured SDG nexus. Although the best model
600 (LUKE) achieved an F1-score of 0.674 on the test set, this performance may not be
601 considered exceptionally high. Several factors contribute to this observation. First, the
602 SDGs are complex and multifaceted, leading to potentially divergent interpretations
603 based on context. Second, our training corpus encompassed a broad range of
604 stakeholders across various sectors and countries and was not labeled according to
605 standardized criteria. As such, the labeling policy likely reflected specific perspectives
606 and stakeholder viewpoints. As Nilsson et al. (2018) highlighted, SDG interactions are
607 influenced by factors such as geographical context, governance structures, and
608 temporal scales. Consequently, stakeholder contexts and objectives can significantly
609 influence implementations and labels. The same can be said of the datasets
610 employed in previous studies. Therefore, the F1-scores observed in this study may
611 reflect the common ground across these diverse interpretations.

612 The best model demonstrated higher generalization performance on the
613 OSDG-CD than other research examples. For example, Kashnitsky et al. (2024)
614 compared the generalization performance of query-based and machine
615 learning-based classification methods and reported that the transformer-based model
616 developed by Vanderfeesten et al. (2022) achieved the highest micro average recall
617 (0.65) on the OSDG-CD. They fine-tuned a multilingual BERT model using the
618 abstracts of 1.4 million papers annotated by a query set. In contrast, our best model
619 was trained on a more targeted yet highly diverse multisector corpus ($n = 23,969$),
620 achieving a higher recall (0.836). This suggests that a corpus incorporating diverse
621 interpretations of SDGs may be crucial to improving generalizability. This aligns with
622 the findings of Wulff et al. (2024), who demonstrated that an ensemble of multiple
623 query-based labeling systems can mitigate individual model biases and enhance
624 overall performance.

625

626 **4.2 Validation of Scientific Attention Imbalance**

627 A critical question is whether the observed imbalance in scientific
628 attention—favoring environmental topics over social ones—is a genuine pattern
629 within the literature or merely an artifact of our classifier's training data distribution. To
630 address this, we conducted a benchmark experiment against a human-coded sample.
631 We randomly sampled 100 articles from our full corpus of 161,520 scientific papers.
632 One of the authors, serving as an SDG domain expert, manually performed a
633 multi-label classification of this sample to create a "human ground truth." We then
634 used our trained LUKE model to predict SDG labels for the same set of 100 articles
635 and compared the results at two levels. First, at the micro-level, we assessed the
636 model's predictive accuracy on these unseen scientific articles. Treating the human
637 labels as the ground truth, the model's predictions achieved a strong macro-averaged
638 F1-score of 0.623 (Precision: 0.782, Recall: 0.518), confirming its reliability at the
639 individual document level. Second, and more importantly, we compared the
640 aggregate SDG distributions at the macro-level. As shown in Figure S3
641 (Supplementary Information), there was a striking alignment between the overall
642 trends identified by the human expert and our model. Both analyses revealed a higher
643 prevalence of articles related to environmental and economic SDGs (e.g., Goals 12,
644 9) compared to those focused on social equity (e.g., Goals 5, 10).

645 This new validation provides strong evidence that the scientific imbalance we
646 report is a genuine pattern in sustainability research and not an artifact of our model.
647 It confirms both the micro-level accuracy of our classifier and the macro-level validity
648 of our central findings regarding the distribution of scientific attention.

649

650 **4.3 LLM coupling for SDG classifiers**

651 LLMs offer boosted SDG classifier development by addressing several
652 limitations related to current approaches. For example, LLMs can generate texts
653 related to specific SDGs to deal with label imbalances in training corpora. Several
654 pioneers have explored this approach, utilizing LLMs to compensate texts of a
655 training corpus (La Fleur 2023; Sashida et al. 2023) and to label the abstracts of

656 academic articles (Kharlashkin et al. 2024). Adams et al. (2023) used ChatGPT
 657 (OpenAI 2022) to enrich keyword lists for query-based classifiers. Other approaches
 658 have employed LLMs to directly classify texts into Global Goals and Targets. Yin et al.
 659 (2023a, 2024) used GPT-4o (OpenAI 2024) and local LLMs (e.g., LLaMA 3 (Meta,
 660 n.d.) and Gamma 2 (Gemma Team et al. 2024)) to classify scientific publications.
 661 Similarly, Garigliotti (2024) used LLMs to detect the relevant targets from
 662 environmental reports. These examples highlight the revolutionary potential of LLMs
 663 to enhance both query-based and machine learning-based SDG classifiers.

664

Table 5 Comparison among query-based model, machine learning-based model, and generative language model.

a) Classification performance on the test set

	Query-based model (text2sdg)			Machine learning-based model (LUKE)			Generative language model (Llama)			Support
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score	
Goal 01	0.573	0.414	0.480	0.573	0.646	0.607	0.743	0.364	0.489	684
Goal 02	0.686	0.491	0.573	0.646	0.688	0.666	0.842	0.409	0.550	702
Goal 03	0.604	0.292	0.393	0.666	0.680	0.673	0.792	0.468	0.588	926
Goal 04	0.635	0.294	0.402	0.673	0.670	0.672	0.702	0.587	0.639	786
Goal 05	0.662	0.401	0.499	0.643	0.634	0.638	0.690	0.521	0.594	724
Goal 06	0.433	0.556	0.487	0.723	0.692	0.707	0.767	0.548	0.639	750
Goal 07	0.485	0.573	0.525	0.649	0.679	0.664	0.707	0.456	0.555	723
Goal 08	0.474	0.270	0.344	0.642	0.655	0.649	0.537	0.535	0.536	972
Goal 09	0.327	0.120	0.175	0.584	0.567	0.576	0.494	0.374	0.426	853
Goal 10	0.286	0.168	0.212	0.521	0.637	0.573	0.574	0.419	0.484	630
Goal 11	0.481	0.304	0.373	0.605	0.628	0.616	0.677	0.374	0.482	967
Goal 12	0.639	0.399	0.491	0.738	0.715	0.727	0.748	0.587	0.658	1,328
Goal 13	0.599	0.667	0.631	0.753	0.695	0.723	0.593	0.726	0.652	1,469
Goal 14	0.885	0.545	0.674	0.843	0.828	0.835	0.913	0.650	0.759	1,549
Goal 15	0.618	0.391	0.479	0.629	0.642	0.635	0.815	0.333	0.473	928
Goal 16	0.551	0.237	0.332	0.591	0.630	0.610	0.569	0.533	0.551	632
Goal 17	0.591	0.278	0.378	0.717	0.631	0.671	0.677	0.445	0.537	1,678
Micro avg.	0.578	0.389	0.465	0.674	0.674	0.674	0.685	0.507	0.582	16,301
Macro avg.	0.561	0.376	0.438	0.658	0.666	0.661	0.696	0.490	0.565	
Weighted avg.	0.582	0.389	0.454	0.678	0.674	0.675	0.703	0.507	0.578	
Samples avg.	0.515	0.480	0.432	0.742	0.753	0.699	0.733	0.645	0.618	

b) Classification performance on OSDG Community Dataset

	Query-based Model (text2sdg)			Machine learning-based Model (LUKE)			Generative Language Model (Llama)			Support
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score	
Goal 01	0.425	0.829	0.562	0.581	0.798	0.672	0.556	0.890	0.685	840
Goal 02	0.433	0.560	0.488	0.705	0.734	0.719	0.737	0.705	0.721	661
Goal 03	0.549	0.869	0.673	0.844	0.912	0.876	0.763	0.960	0.850	1,470
Goal 04	0.576	0.818	0.676	0.814	0.927	0.867	0.701	0.957	0.809	1,694
Goal 05	0.709	0.864	0.779	0.851	0.789	0.819	0.801	0.900	0.848	1,904
Goal 06	0.367	0.868	0.516	0.908	0.803	0.852	0.834	0.858	0.846	1,226
Goal 07	0.596	0.890	0.714	0.860	0.868	0.864	0.800	0.917	0.854	1,279
Goal 08	0.121	0.715	0.207	0.327	0.721	0.450	0.200	0.929	0.329	702
Goal 09	0.223	0.724	0.340	0.569	0.718	0.635	0.494	0.876	0.632	823
Goal 10	0.097	0.737	0.171	0.320	0.655	0.430	0.241	0.782	0.368	487
Goal 11	0.248	0.768	0.375	0.734	0.804	0.768	0.774	0.839	0.806	965
Goal 12	0.122	0.886	0.214	0.262	0.856	0.401	0.500	0.886	0.639	167
Goal 13	0.343	0.897	0.496	0.682	0.823	0.746	0.390	0.948	0.553	757
Goal 14	0.630	0.891	0.738	0.778	0.946	0.854	0.766	0.924	0.838	607
Goal 15	0.512	0.898	0.652	0.777	0.924	0.844	0.826	0.912	0.867	581
Goal 16	0.335	0.760	0.465	0.826	0.909	0.865	0.693	0.945	0.799	1,575
Micro avg.	0.352	0.817	0.492	0.702	0.836	0.763	0.591	0.902	0.714	
Macro avg.	0.393	0.811	0.504	0.677	0.824	0.729	0.630	0.889	0.715	15,738
Weighted avg.	0.447	0.817	0.559	0.747	0.836	0.781	0.677	0.902	0.757	
Samples avg.	0.427	0.817	0.525	0.753	0.836	0.779	0.705	0.902	0.764	

665

666 To further explore the potential of LLMs, we conducted a simple experiment
667 to compare the performance of three different approaches to SDG classification: a
668 query-based model, machine learning-based model, and a generative language
669 model in Table 5. As the query-based model, the detect_sdg method in the text2sdg
670 R package was employed, which ensembles six query-based labeling systems using
671 a random forest. The machine learning-based model was our best model of LUKE.
672 For the generative language model, we employed Llama-3.1-70B-Instruct
673 (meta-llama 2024), an open-source local LLM that does not rely on an online
674 application programming interface. The prompt for this model was tuned up by
675 referring Skrynnik et al. (2024). Table 5 a) presents the performance on the test set
676 from our multi-labeled training corpus. The machine learning-based model achieved
677 the highest F1-score (0.674), followed by the generative language model (0.582), and
678 the query-based model (0.465). Notably, the generative language model, without any
679 specialized fine-tuning, outperformed the query-based model, demonstrating a strong
680 understanding of the SDGs. The performance on the single-label OSDG-CD is
681 detailed in Table 5 b). The generative language model achieved the highest recall
682 (0.902), surpassing both the machine learning-based model (0.836) and the

683 query-based model (0.817). From a multi-label classification perspective, the
684 machine learning-based model trained with the multi-labeled training corpus may be
685 more suitable than the generative language model. However, the generative
686 language model could potentially acquire multi-label classification capabilities by
687 incorporating external knowledge about SDG interlinkages via prompt-tuning. This
688 indicates that further LLM research is needed to advance the SDG research.

689

690 **4.4 Detecting the key concepts of the SDG nexus**

a): Developed and emerging research nexus (Goals 05 and 12)

b): Biosphere-Society-Economy nexus (Goals 07, 12, and 15)

Fig. 9 Word co-occurrence networks illustrating key concepts related to the nexuses between Global Goals in the scientific articles. The edge width is dependent on the number of co-occurrences between words. The sizes of texts and nodes are proportional to the weighted degree of nodes. The nodes are colored according to the

communities identified by the modularity optimization algorithm.

691 In the result section, the best model illustrated the strength and weakness of
692 SDG nexus within the scientific attention. Here, we discuss the central concept of
693 transdisciplinarity (Lang et al. 2012) to strengthen the SDG integration. The
694 prominent concepts within the two SDG nexuses are illustrated in Fig. 9. Fig. 9 a)
695 shows the key themes of 25 articles predicted to be relevant to Goal 12, a
696 well-established area with numerous publications, and Goal 05, an emerging area
697 with comparatively fewer publications, shown in Fig. 4 and 5. The extracted keywords
698 include “gender,” “woman,” “consumption,” and “company.” These keywords, for
699 example, appear in the research by García Martín and Herrero (2020) who examines
700 the relationship between board gender diversity and corporate environmental
701 performance in terms of sustainable production. Similarly, Barrera-Verdugo and
702 Villarroel-Villarroel (2022) investigated the influence of gender on sustainable
703 consumption behavior, and Isenhour and Ardenfors (2009) argued that gender
704 inequality prevents the realization of sustainable consumption. These studies and our
705 findings suggest that gender equality is both a driver and a prerequisite for
706 sustainable consumption and production. The Goal 05 - 12 nexus, therefore,
707 represents a promising area for innovative equality research such as realizing
708 sustainable consumption and production in all gender.

709 Fig. 9 b) shows an example of the prominent concepts from 113 articles
710 predicted to be relevant to Goals 7, 12, and 15, representing Biosphere, Society, and
711 Economy as three layers depicted in the SDGs Wedding Cake model (Folke et al.
712 2016; Stockholm Resilience Center 2016). The central themes are biomass and
713 bioenergy. Many notable articles have examined biomass resource circulation, such
714 as the utilization of agricultural residues (Mattias et al. 2021), vineyard pruning (Giorio
715 et al. 2019), waste biomass (Oyebanji et al. 2023), wood (P. W. R. Adams &
716 McManus 2014), and food (Koido et al. 2018). Other articles have addressed lifecycle
717 assessments (Cusenza et al. 2021), economic analyses of microbial fuel cells for
718 bioelectricity generation (Hoang et al. 2022), and sustainability criteria for biomass
719 production and utilization (Hämäläinen et al. 2011). These studies and our findings
720 suggest that bioenergy may be a key innovation area that will drive the transition from

721 a current circular economy, which aims to minimize resource consumption and waste
722 generation to improve resource efficiency (Geissdoerfer et al. 2017), to a future
723 circular bioeconomy, which emphasizes the sustainable use of renewable biological
724 resources (Ferraz & Pyka 2023; Venkatesh 2022).

725 **5. Conclusion**

726 This study developed a highly generalizable multi-label text classification
727 model to translate diverse sustainability efforts to an interconnected SDG nexus
728 structure. Leveraging a novel training corpus collected from diverse sectors and
729 countries, our best model based on the LUKE achieved high generalization
730 performance, as demonstrated by its strong recall on the OSDG-CD.

731 To demonstrate the utility of the best model for SDG nexus analysis, we
732 investigated the distribution and interrelationships of SDGs within the corpus of
733 sustainability research articles, revealing high scientific attention on resource
734 efficiency and climate change and comparatively sparse attention to social issues,
735 such as gender equality and justice. However, we identified key connections among
736 seemingly disparate themes through Global Goals related to poverty, health, decent
737 work, and economic growth. Our model also highlighted bioenergy as a potential
738 bridge linking environmental, social, and economic sustainability, underscoring the
739 model's capacity to uncover complex interconnections within the SDG framework.

740 Our model achieved what we believe to be very high performance among SDG
741 machine learning-based classifiers. However, future research should explore the
742 integration of additional generative language models. These evolving technologies
743 hold promise for accelerating the attainment of sustainable and just future by
744 facilitating collaborative and integrated SDG implementations.

745

746 **Acknowledgements**

747 This work was supported by the Environment Research and Technology
748 Development Fund (JPMEERF23S12100, JPMEERF23S12116, and
749 JPMEERF20211004, JPMEERF20251004) of the Ministry of Environment of Japan
750 and the Environmental Restoration and Conservation Agency of Japan.

751 **Data and Code Availability**

752 The fine-tuned LUKE model presented in this study is publicly available on the Hugging Face
753 Model Hub at: [<https://huggingface.co/GE-Lab/SDGs-classifier>]. The complete Python code
754 for data preprocessing, model training, and nexus analysis is available in our GitHub
755 repository: [<https://github.com/Green-Engineers-Lab/SDGs-classifier/>]. The training corpus
756 was compiled from publicly available sources. While the compiled corpus cannot be
757 redistributed directly due to the terms of use of the original sources, a detailed list of all
758 sources and instructions for their collection are provided in the Supplementary Information
759 (S4) to ensure full reproducibility.

760 **Authors contribution**

761 NM, TM, and SK devised the project, and NM and TM established the main
762 conceptual ideas and proof outline. NM, TM, and CH worked out all of the technical
763 details and performed the corpus data collection and coding for machine learning
764 implementation and related applications. NM, TM, CH, NM2, and SK joined the
765 discussion and upgraded the information. NM and TM wrote the draft manuscript, and
766 all members reviewed and contributed to its finalization.

767

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1276 **Supplementary Material**

1277 **S1. Label Consistency Validation of the Training Corpus**

1278 The SDG labels in our training corpus were self-declared by the originating
1279 entities. To assess their consistency, we conducted a validation study. We randomly
1280 sampled 110 documents (10 from each of the 11 sources). An SDG domain expert
1281 then re-labeled these documents for all 17 Goals without seeing the original labels.

1282 Using the expert's labels as the ground truth, we evaluated the original
1283 self-declared labels. The macro-averaged F1-score was 0.57, with a precision of 0.44
1284 and a recall of 0.82. This result confirms that the original labels possess a reasonable
1285 degree of validity. The high recall indicates that the labels effectively capture relevant
1286 SDG themes, while the lower precision suggests they are sometimes applied broadly,
1287 a common feature of self-reported data.

1288 To contextualize the labeling consistency, we also had two Large Language
1289 Models (GPT-4o and Gemini-2.5-flash) classify the same 110 documents. We then
1290 measured the agreement among the Human Expert, GPT-4o, and Gemini-2.5-flash.
1291 The mean pairwise F1-score among all three annotators was 0.655. This substantial
1292 agreement level highlights a shared understanding of SDG classification among the
1293 human expert and leading LLMs, while also underscoring the inherent complexity and
1294 interpretive nature of the task.

1295

1296 **S2. Justification for Cosine Similarity Threshold Selection**

1297 The construction of the SDG Target network, a central component of our
1298 nexus analysis, relies on a cosine similarity threshold. We recognize that this
1299 threshold is a critical parameter that shapes the final network topology and its
1300 interpretation. To ensure our choice of threshold was robust and data-driven, we
1301 conducted an analysis to identify the optimal threshold that best reveals an
1302 interpretable community structure within the Target network. We generated multiple
1303 Target networks by varying the cosine similarity threshold for article-Target relevance
1304 from 0.1 to 0.9 in increments of 0.1. For each threshold, we constructed the Target
1305 network. For each resulting network, we calculated its modularity. Modularity is a
1306 standard metric that quantifies the strength of a network's division into communities,
1307 with higher scores indicating a more well-defined structure.

1308

1309

1310 Figure S1. Network Modularity as a Function of the Cosine Similarity Threshold.

1311

1312 The relationship between the cosine similarity threshold and the network's

1313 modularity is shown in Figure S1. Modularity begins to increase significantly at a
1314 threshold of 0.7 and reaches its maximum value at 0.9. This suggests that thresholds
1315 within the 0.7-0.9 range are most likely to yield networks with meaningful community
1316 structures.

1317
1318 a) Threshold = 0.7
1319

1320

1321 b) Threshold = 0.8

1322

1323

1324 c) Threshold = 0.9

1325 Figure S2. Dendrograms of Target Clustering at Different Similarity Thresholds. a)
1326 Threshold = 0.7, b) Threshold = 0.8 (as in main text), c) Threshold = 0.9.

1327

1328 While modularity provides a quantitative guide, the ultimate goal is to enable
1329 an insightful interpretation of the Target nexuses. We therefore performed a
1330 qualitative inspection of the dendrograms generated for the three high-modularity
1331 thresholds: 0.7, 0.8, and 0.9 (Figure S2). At the 0.9 threshold, which maximized
1332 modularity, the network became overly fragmented. Many Targets formed their own
1333 small clusters or were isolated, making it difficult to identify meaningful nexuses
1334 between different Goals. The structure was too granular to be useful for an integrated
1335 analysis. Conversely, the 0.7 threshold resulted in a network with fewer, larger
1336 communities. This coarse structure tended to merge distinct concepts, obscuring the
1337 more nuanced relationships that are critical for understanding inter-Target dynamics.
1338 The 0.8 threshold provided the best balance. It yielded a high modularity score while
1339 producing a network with a clear, interpretable community structure, revealing distinct
1340 yet interconnected communities. Based on this integrated analysis, which combined a
1341 quantitative assessment of modularity with a qualitative evaluation of the resulting
1342 network's interpretability, we concluded that a cosine similarity threshold of 0.8 is the
1343 most appropriate and robust choice for achieving the objectives of our nexus
1344 analysis.

1345

1346 **S3. Validation of Scientific Attention Imbalance against Human**
 1347 **Coding**

1348 To verify that the observed imbalance in scientific attention towards different
 1349 SDGs (reported in Section 3.4) is a genuine phenomenon and not a bias introduced
 1350 by our classifier, we benchmarked our model's macro-level predictions against a
 1351 human-coded ground truth.

1352 We randomly sampled 100 scientific articles from the full corpus of 161,520
 1353 papers used in our study. An SDG domain expert manually assigned multi-label SDG
 1354 classifications to each of these 100 articles. We then applied our trained LUKE model
 1355 to predict labels for the same sample.

1356

1357

1358 Figure S3. SDG Label Distributions by Human Coding on a Sample of 100
 1359 Scientific Articles.

1360

1361 The primary goal of this analysis was to compare the aggregate distribution of
 1362 SDG labels assigned by the human expert versus those predicted by the LUKE model.

1363 Figure S3 shows the number of articles assigned to each SDG by both the human
1364 coder and the model.

1365 The results demonstrate a strong alignment in the overall distribution. Both
1366 methods identified Goal 12 as the most frequent, and Goals 5 as the least frequent.
1367 This high degree of correspondence in the macro-level trend confirms that the
1368 imbalance in scientific attention reported in our main findings is reflective of the
1369 underlying data, not an artifact of our model's predictive behavior.

1370

1371 **S4. Data Sources and Corpus Reconstruction Protocol**

1372 Our training corpus was constructed by collecting documents explicitly linked to the
 1373 Global Goals from 11 diverse, multi-sectoral sources spanning industry, government,
 1374 academia, and civil society. The sources were selected based on two primary criteria: (1) the
 1375 associated Global Goals were assigned by human experts rather than through automated or
 1376 keyword-based methods, and (2) the data supported multi-labeling, where a single document
 1377 could be associated with multiple SDGs. The details of each source are provided in Table S1.

1378

1379 **Table S1: Detailed List of Data Sources for Training Corpus Reconstruction**

Source ID	Source Name	Description and Origin	URL / Access Method	Collection Notes
01	SDGs Definition	Official definitions of the 17 Goals, 169 Targets, and 231 global indicators. Origin: United Nations.	https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/indicators-list/	The full text of all definitions, targets, and indicators was used.
02	UN SDGs Progress	Annual progress reports on the SDGs. Origin: United Nations.	https://documents.un.org/	Paragraphs were extracted from the annual reports published from 2016 to 2023.
03	SDG Actions Platform	A platform for sharing SDG-related activities by diverse stakeholders. Origin: United Nations.	https://sdgs.un.org/partnerships	Documents and activity descriptions registered by governments, NGOs, businesses, etc., were collected.
04	SDG Knowledge Hub	News articles, guest articles, and policy briefs related to the SDGs. Origin: International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD).	https://sdg.iisd.org/news/	All relevant English-language articles were scraped and collected.
05	Japanese Cabinet	The official SDGs Action Plan of the Japanese government. Origin: Cabinet Office of Japan.	https://www.kantei.go.jp/jp/singi/sdgs/index.html	The full text of the action plan was used.
06	Plastics Smart	A platform for initiatives by diverse stakeholders addressing plastic pollution. Origin: Ministry of the Environment, Japan.	https://plastics-smart.env.go.jp/case/	Descriptions of registered initiatives were scraped and collected.
07	PANCES	A list of policies related to biodiversity and ecosystem conservation. Origin: National Institute for Environmental Studies, Japan.	https://www.nies.go.jp/pances/search/	The text of listed policies was collected.
08	Zenkoku Net	A database of local decarbonization efforts. Origin: Japan Network for Climate Change Actions.	https://www.zenkoku-net.org/datsutanso/database/	Descriptions of registered local projects were scraped and collected.
09	EXPO 2025	A platform for SDG-related actions by participants of the 2025 World Exposition in Osaka. Origin: Japan Association for the 2025 World Exposition.	https://team.expo2025.or.jp/ja/challenge https://team.expo2025.or.jp/ja/partner	Descriptions of participant actions and initiatives were scraped and collected.
10	Osaka University	SDG-related research, education, and outreach activities. Origin: Osaka University.	https://sdgs.osaka-u.ac.jp/	Descriptions of university-led projects and initiatives were scraped and collected.
11	Hokkaido University	SDG-related research, education, and outreach activities. Origin: Hokkaido University.	https://sdgs.hokudai.ac.jp/en/	Descriptions of university-led projects and initiatives were scraped and collected.

1380

1381 **Note on Translation:** The texts from sources 05 through 11 were originally in Japanese and were
 1382 translated into English using the Google Translate API via the Python deep-translator library
 1383 (Baccouri, 2020/2024).

1384

1385 All collected texts underwent minimal preprocessing: they were normalized using
 1386 Normalization Form Compatibility Composition (NFKC) (Python, n.d.), and extraneous
 1387 whitespace was removed. No further preprocessing, such as stop-word removal or stemming,
 1388 was performed. This minimalistic approach was chosen because it has been reported that for
 1389 deep learning-based NLP models, excessive preprocessing can hinder performance by removing
 1390 contextual information crucial for understanding the overall meaning of a sentence (Alzahrani &
 1391 Jololian, 2021).

1392